

LOCAL GOVERNMENT AUTONOMY AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT IN IHIALA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined effects of local government autonomy on rural development in Ihiala local government area of Anambra State, Nigeria. The objective of the study was to ascertain the effect of local government administrative autonomy on administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria. Flowing from the specific objectives of the study, three research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study was anchored on the theory of decentralization. The researcher adopted descriptive survey research design. Structured questionnaire was used for collection of primary data and data collected were presented and analyzed using tables and percentages. Findings revealed that local government administrative autonomy has a significant effect on administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria. It was also discovered, among other, that there is a significant relationship between local government political autonomy and provision of health centers in Ihiala local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommended that local council authorities should be allowed greater flexibility to recruit and manage their personnel in line with their peculiar needs, challenges and resources.

Introduction

Local government administration has been adopted as the main fundamental instrument for the acceleration and sustenance of rural development (Agbodike, Igbokwe-Ibeto & Nkah, 2014). It serves as vehicle for political education and mobilization among others. Several efforts

have been made towards moving the system from local administration to local government with functional political and economic autonomy (Agbodike, Igbokwe-Ibeto & Nkah, 2014). The political and administrative structure of Nigeria is a thirty-six states federal structure with the Federal Capital Territory (FCT, Abuja) bringing

Ezinwa Precious Onyekwere and Chinyeaka J. Igbokwe-Ibeto

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it up to thirty-seven. There are also 774 local government systems spread across the thirty-seven subnational governance structures in the country. This makes the local government the third level of government after the federal and state governments (Akhakpe, 2021). The local government system in Nigeria has continued to attract considerable attention in recent times. The crux of the attention, which are sometimes positive or negative, boils down to the issue of performance of the local government as a system of government and the attainment of the goals of grassroots development.

According to Akindiyo, Imoukhuede, and Mohammed, (2015) the Nigerian local government system is crises ridden on account of its failure to perform its statutory duties, thus, undermining its very existence. In interrogating the many issues plaguing, the local government system in Nigeria, it is important to stress that the local government in Nigeria is a creation of the constitution. Section 7 (1) of the 1999 constitution of Nigeria, as amended, provides for the existence of a system of local government operated by democratically elected local council officials. Also, the guidelines for the 1976 reform of local government in Nigeria sees the local government as a government at the local level exercised through representative council established by law to exercise specific powers within defined areas. These powers should give the council authorities substantial control over local affairs. The substantial control should include powers over the staff of the councils, institutional as well as financial powers to

initiate and execute projects and provide social services to complement the activities of the state and federal government in their areas. This is to be achieved through the active participation of the people and their institutions, especially traditional institutions, Civil Society Organizations, Community and Faith Based Organizations, among others.

It presupposes from the foregoing, that the local government is supposed to enjoy some measure of autonomy. The question of autonomy here arises as a result of the fact that in Nigeria and many other countries of the world where the local government exists, it is usually a subnational government that often ranks below the federal (or central) government and other regional (or state) government in existence. This means that the local government operates side by side other higher levels of government in a sovereign state.

In many states of the federation, especially in Anambra state, the local government has continued to exist as a department of the state government. The state government does not only manage their statutory allocations but deprives them of their ability to generate revenue internally (Mahmud & Ogwuzebe, 2020). Between 2006 and 2023, which include the eight years administration of former Governors Peter Obi (2006 – 2014) and Willie Obiano (2014 – 2022) and two years of Prof Chukwuma Soludo (2022 – 2024) as governor of Anambra State, local government elections were not conducted. This portrays a lack of political autonomy for the local government. To avoid leadership vacuum,

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state governors operated with either Caretaker Committee Chairmen or Transition Committee Chairmen.

The Fourth Schedule of 1979 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, outlined in details, the development functions of local governments in Nigeria. Local governments have responsibility for primary education, agriculture, primary health services, construction and maintenance of rural roads and rural markets, among other functions. The execution of these functions by the local government, which are expressly spelt out in the residual list of the 1999 constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria, requires that the local government must have sufficient autonomy and leeway to effectively articulate and execute development functions in their various localities (Olaoye, 2018).

The 2024 landmark judgement of the Nigerian Supreme Court with respect to local government autonomy forced state governors, including the Anambra state governor, to conduct local government elections in order for the local governments within their domains to be entitled to statutory allocations. While the conduct of local government elections was supposed to pave the way for the political autonomy of the local government, analyses of the elections conducted by the State Independent Electoral Commission in many states, including Anambra state, show that while the constitution and the courts intend to make the local government autonomous, the state governors are not ready to grant substantial autonomy to the local government within their domains (Zango & Mohammed, 2025).

Ihiala local government, being at the periphery with proximity to Imo state is faced with peculiar developmental challenges that is common to border communities. Presently, the town of Orsumoghu that shares border with Orsu local government area in Imo State has become a dangerous enclave for unknown gunmen and terrorists masquerading as agitators. The years of government neglect of Orsumoghu, occasioned by the lack of autonomy and functionality of the local government system, has created a governance, social and security crises in the area, affecting the provision of basic social amenities like road infrastructure, healthcare, among other amenities. In view of the foregoing, this study seeks to examine effect of local government autonomy on rural development in Ihiala Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Out of the many problems besetting the local government system in the Nigerian federation, the question of autonomy ranks high. Autonomy could be in the forms of political, administrative or financial autonomy. Political autonomy exists when the local government councils are operated by democratically elected chairmen and councilors, who are freely and fairly elected. The conduct of elections into elective positions in the local government in every state in Nigeria is the responsibility of the State Independent Electoral Commissions established under section 197(1)(b) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.

Ezinwa Precious Onyekwere and Chinyeaka J. Igbokwe-Ibeto

The multiparty democracy in operation in Nigeria, makes the conduct of elections into executive and legislative positions in the local government a thorny issue. In Anambra state, a culmination of court cases and lack of political will stalled the conduct of local government for over a decade. The lack of elected representatives in Ihiala Local Government has affected the ability of the local government leadership to effectively articulate the peculiar needs of the people in the local government, thereby affecting their developmental prospects. Also, the issue of administrative autonomy for the local government is almost nonexistent. In every state executive structure, there is the Ministry of local government, including the Local Government Service Commission. In Anambra state specifically, there is also the State and Local Government Joint Account Committee that manages the finances of the local government, especially its statutory allocations. By implication, the local governments cannot employ high level manpower without inputs and approvals from their respective state governments. Thus, while the Ministry of local government and the Local Government Service Commission at the state level supervise the administrative operations of the local government, the State and Local Government Joint Account Committee supervises the financial activities of the local government.

The existence of the state and local government joint account has placed huge limitations on the ability of the local government to effectively manage their local affairs and administer their

constitutional functions and duties, thus, reducing the local governments to appendages of the state government. Therefore, while modalities are being put in place to effectively implement the Supreme Court judgement of 2024 on local government autonomy, this present study examines the effect of local government autonomy on rural development in Ihiala Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

To investigate the effect of local government autonomy on rural development in Ihiala local government area, Anambra state South East Nigeria in this study, efforts were made to beam our search light on the following two research questions:

1. To what extent will administrative autonomy significantly affect administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria?
2. To what extent will local government political autonomy significantly affect the provision of health centers in Ihiala local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

To determine the effect of local government autonomy on rural development in Ihiala local government area, Anambra state in South-East Nigeria, the following two research hypotheses were tested for the purpose of this research:

1. **H₀:** Local government administrative autonomy has no significant effect on administration of primary education in Ihiala

Ezinwa Precious Onyekwere and Chinyeaka J. Igbokwe-Ibeto

local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria.

2. **Ho:** There is no significant relationship between local government political autonomy and provision of health centers in Ihiala local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

Conceptual and Theoretical Review

Local government as a concept has attracted several definitions. But unlike other concepts, it has not generated much controversy as to its actual meaning. A sketch of some of these definitions could be helpful. Local government according to Agbodike, Igbokwe-Ibeto & Nkah (2014) can be defined as the substructure upon which the superstructures of state and federal governments are erected. In the views of Lawal and Oladunjoye (2020), local government is that tier of government closest to the people, which are vested with certain powers to exercise control over the affairs of the people in its domain. There are general features in all of the definitions. One of such features is the fact that the local government is a government within a government. It is also generally perceived as an administrative and governance structure that exists as part of a wider government in a political system. According to Chaturvedi in (Anazodo, Igbokwe-Ibeto & Nkomah, 2016) local government autonomy is the granting of authority to a political organization within a geographical area to decide and determine its own course of action.

Development means the capacity of a national economy whose initial economic conditions has been more or less static for a long time, to

generate and sustain an annual increase in its Gross National Product (GNP) at rates of perhaps five to seven percent or more (Okoye, 2014). Rural development is a component of the overall goal of national development. It is the transformation that takes place in areas that are outside the city centers. A rural area is that geographic region that is outside the purview of the urban areas. It is often characterized by limited access to essential services and amenities, poor infrastructure, among others. It is often speculated that majority of the Nigerian population live in the rural areas. This makes rural development the foundation of national development.

Theoretically, this study anchored on decentralization theory. The decentralization theory does not have a single originator in the way that some classical theories do. Rather, it has evolved over time through contributions from multiple scholars, political thinkers, and institutions. However, several key figures and schools of thought have significantly influenced the development and formalisation of decentralisation theory. However, Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1762) can be considered the earliest contributor to the theory of decentralization, who, in his essay on the Social Contract, emphasized the idea of popular sovereignty and participatory governance, which laid the foundation behind the decentralization theory. He advocated that governance should be close to the people, to reflect the "general will". While the decentralisation theory has many advocates, it has also attracted significant criticism. Ostrom

Ezinwa Precious Onyekwere and Chinyeaka J. Igbokwe-Ibeto

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(1993), although supportive of the decentralization theory, warned of possible issues with coordination among tiers of government, leading to fragmentation and lack of coordination.

Local Government and the unending quest for Autonomy

The idea of autonomy in political discourse is indicative of the ability of an institution or a political entity to exercise substantial control over its affairs or territory. For the local government system in Nigeria, the question of autonomy is topical and the debate appears to be endless. For one, local governments exist as a subnational within a larger governance framework. Because of its position as a smaller governance unit within a larger government architecture, it would appear to mean that the issue of autonomy for local government is a wild goose chase. However, the local government reform of 1976 in Nigeria, provided not only a definition for local government, but also outlined the basic principles of local government autonomy. According to the 1976 reform document, local government is defined as: Government at the local level exercised through Representative Council established by law to exercise specific powers within defined areas. These powers should give the council substantial control over local affairs as well as the staff... institutional and financial powers to initiate and direct the provision of services and to determine and implement projects so as to implement the activities of the state and federal government in their areas, and to ensure, through devolution of

these functions to these Councils and through the active participation of the people and their traditional institutions, that local initiative and response to local needs and conditions are maximized.

Certain key elements of local government autonomy are evident in the above definition. First, is the fact that the local government is a creation of law, thus, having a legal personality that is distinct from those of the state and federal governments. Secondly, the local government is expected to derive its powers and functions from the same constitution just as it is with the state and federal governments, and not to be tale-guided by other higher levels of government. Thirdly, the local government is constitutionally expected to operate independently of the state and federal governments. That implies that the local government is not an offshoot or branch office of the federal or state government. Fourthly, the local government is empowered the ability to make its own rules, regulations and laws as it pertains to local affairs. Finally, local government is constitutionally empowered to formulate and implement its own policies and programmes, as well as the right to recruit, train, develop promote and discipline its own staff.

Local Government Political Autonomy and the Provision of Primary Healthcare

One major pointer to the political autonomy of the local government is in the area of its leadership not being appointed by other levels of government, but being a product of a free and fair electoral process from where the people freely choose who to govern them at the

Ezinwa Precious Onyekwere and Chinyeaka J. Igbokwe-Ibeto

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grassroots level. An election is an official decision-making process by which a population chooses an individual to hold public office for a constitutionally specified period of time (Alfa, Ahmadu and Adah, 2013). Elections have been the usual mechanism by which modern representative democracies operate since the 17th century (Encyclopedia Britannica, cited in Alfa, Ahmadu and Adah, 2013). Elections are the means through which the people exercise their sovereign right to choose who governs them and what the political and other priorities of their government should be. Democratic elections are thus the opportunity for the people to express their sovereignty through the ballot to confer legitimacy to their government, renew its mandate if necessary or withdraw from it the authority to govern. This is the basis of accountable government. (INEC, 2011).

In a democratic state, periodic elections into executive and legislative positions constitute the primary established model for making sure that the government derives its just powers from the willful consensus of the governed. Elections are central to the functioning of modern democracy (Singh and Mishra, 1991). The objective in any electoral process is to establish the intent of the voter, and through it transfer the intent to the vote counter. The efficiency of the voting method and the accuracy of the vote counting are the crucial determinants of the ability and capacity of the system to correctly determine the wish of the voter (Iwu, 2008).

In Nigeria, the conduct of elections into elective positions in the local government has been a

thorny issue. Some state governors are more comfortable with appointing caretaker committees to run the affairs of the local government areas in their domain than organising local government elections. This is because the caretaker committees, as appointees of the governor, hold office at the pleasure of the governors and can be removed at will by the governor. Even when locally elected representatives are in place, there have been instances where a governor will unilaterally dissolve the council, especially when the elections that ushered in the local government chairmen and councilors were conducted by a previous administration.

The legal, political and administrative quagmire has prompted local government scholars and experts in Nigeria to coin the terms local government and local administration in order to differentiate a constitutionally recognised local government set up, from one that is an appendage of the state government. Thus, to Akhakpe, (2021), what distinguishes local government from local administration is the degree of autonomy that the local government enjoys in carrying out its activities. Continuing, Akhakpe (2021), stressed that such autonomy would reflect the degree of powers, functions and resources at its disposal subject, of course, to the test of reasonableness.

Local Government Administrative Autonomy and Administrative Efficiency

In our discussion on local government autonomy, it is important to note that there is no political system that the local units operate

Ezinwa Precious Onyekwere and Chinyeaka J. Igbokwe-Ibeto

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completely independent of the central or regional or state government (Akpan, & Ekanem, 2013). In the colonial era, local government enjoyed a wide range of both financial and administrative autonomy. The local government system was largely derived from the British Whitehall model. The colonial government allowed each region to oversee the activities of their local affairs under its jurisdiction. This means that the legal framework for local government was provided for by each region: The Eastern region local government ordinance of 1950, the Western region local government law of 1952 and the 1954 native authority law in Northern Nigeria (Akpan, & Ekanem, 2013). During this period, the councils were given a wide range of functions including primary education, health, police, and judiciary among others. Furthermore, the councils also enjoyed a great measure of autonomy in financial, personnel and general administration. In other words, the local governments were under the regional governments and there was relatively little or no interference in the activities of local governments by the federal government. The reason for this is not farfetched. The local governments were offshoots of the native authority system that were in existence before, or created by the British colonialists. They were formidable structures that the British used to administer the country through indirect rule.

It is a fact that has been established earlier in this study that the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria in Section 7(1) recognizes the local government as a level of government in the

Nigerian federation. Yet, the state government through the Ministry of Local Government, Local Government Service Commission, Caretaker Committee and appointment of Transition Committee Chairmen (TC Chairmen) / Sole Administrators to oversee the activities of local government in their domain, continue to treat the local government as a liaison office of the state government. Local councils are not allowed to employ technocrats and other categories of senior civil servants on their payroll. Also, staff of the local government, through the Local Government Service Commission, transfer local government staff from one local government to the other, a feature not practicable with state government employees.

Having a state agency like the Local Government Service Commission oversee the administrative workings of the local government does not effectively guarantee administrative efficiency. A situation where local government workers are transferred from one local government council to the other comes at huge administrative cost to all the affected local governments and the personnel involved. The staff will have to physically relocate and begin to integrate afresh with the new community where he or she has been posted to. The time it will take for such staff to settle to the new environment and the new office is one cost that is often being overlooked. Alternatively, it also presents a situation where the worker is forced to operate from a distant location and offer skeletal services because of time and distance barriers.

Methodology

Ezinwa Precious Onyekwere and Chinyeaka J. Igbokwe-Ibeto

This study adopted survey research design. Survey design is one in which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. It specifies how such data will be collected and analyzed. This method was chosen for data collection, because it enabled the researcher to solicit for information that might not be available on the pages of the text book.

The population of the study consisted of the staff of Ihiala local government council and the

residents of Ihiala local government area. According to data from the Anambra State Local Government Service Commission in December of 2024, Ihiala local government council has a total of 154 staff. Also, the local government area has a total inhabitant of 430,800, according to the 2022 population projection by the National Population Commission. The population distribution, showing the different departments of the local government staff, is presented in table 3.1 below;

Table 1: Population Distribution of the Ihiala Local Government Staff

S/N	Départements	Population
1	Administration and Personnel	26
2	Treasury and Finance	11
3	Works and Infrastructure	14
4	Health	12
5	Education	28
6	Agriculture and Natural Resources Development	19
7	Social Welfare	11
8	Environment	10
9	Revenue	15
10	Data, Statistics and Planning	8
	Total	154

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The study assumes that the 154 staff of the local government resides in the locality and constitute part of the 430,800. In determining the sample

size, Taro Yamane formula was used. The Taro Yamane formula was adopted because the sample size is definite and known. This formula is as follows:

Ezinwa Precious Onyekwere and Chinyeaka J. Igbokwe-Ibeto

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where n = sample size

N = Population of the study

e = Sampling error (in this case 5 percent)

The sample size is therefore computed as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{430,800}{1+430,800(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{430,800}{1+430,800(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{430,800}{1+1077}$$

$$n = \frac{430,800}{1078}$$

$$n = 400$$

Having determined the sample size, bearing in mind, the fact that the population was unevenly distributed because while Ihiala local government area has a population figure 430,800, the local government council has a population of 154. To this end, adopting a statistical tool to arrive at a proportionate figure for each segment of the population will see some segments of the population getting less than one questionnaire allocated to it.

$$ns = Np \times n \frac{\quad}{N}$$

ns = Sample size allocated to each unit

Np = Population size of each unit

n = Total sample size

N = Total population size

Therefore, the sample allocation to each department in the local government is determined as follows:

Ezinwa Precious Onyekwere and Chinyeaka J. Igbokwe-Ibeto

Table 2: Population Distribution of the Ihiala Local Government Staff

S/N	Départements	Population
1	Administration and Personnel	$\frac{26 \times 100}{154} = 17$
2	Treasury and Finance	$\frac{11 \times 100}{154} = 7$
3	Works and Infrastructure	$\frac{14 \times 100}{154} = 9$
4	Health	$\frac{12 \times 100}{154} = 8$
5	Education	$\frac{28 \times 100}{154} = 18$
6	Agriculture and Natural Resources Development	$\frac{19 \times 100}{154} = 12$
7	Social Welfare	$\frac{11 \times 100}{154} = 7$
8	Environment	$\frac{10 \times 100}{154} = 7$
9	Revenue	$\frac{15 \times 100}{154} = 10$
10	Data, Statistics and Planning	$\frac{8 \times 100}{154} = 5$
	Total	100

Source: Researchers computation, 2025

The justification for this statistical tool is that it helps to eliminate researcher's bias and ensures that the sample allocation is proportionate and a true representation of the total population size of the study. Having determined the sample allocation size of each department in the local

government, the researcher proceeded to determine the staffs that participated in the study. Based on this, **N** small cards with numbers 1-100 and 1-50 as the case may be, will be prepared for the sampling and will be put in a box. Then, the **n** cards will be randomly picked and those that selected **1** to the actual number

Ezinwa Precious Onyekwere and Chinyeaka J. Igbokwe-Ibeto

required for each institution automatically become part of the sample from the local government council. The respondents who are residents of the local government will also be selected as the second segment of the participants for the study, using the same method of random selection in order to ensure that they are given equal opportunity of representation.

Presentation and Analysis of Data According to Research Questions

The researcher distributed a total of four hundred (400) questionnaires of ten (10) items each to sampled respondents. As a result of frequent persuasion on the importance of responding fully and honestly to the questionnaire, the researcher was able to achieve

questionnaire return of three hundred and fifty-three (353) responses while seventeen (17) were not returned out of the total distributed four hundred (400). Out of these numbers, ten (10) copies of the questionnaire were not properly filled, leaving a total of three hundred and forty-three (343) usable questionnaires yielding a response rate of 86percent. The researchers proceeded with the analysis of the data as 86percent response rate is regarded as very satisfactory for this study. This is corroborated by Igbokwe-Ibeto (2019), who argued that some rules of thumb about the return/response rate is that a response rate of 50percent is adequate for analysis and reporting, 60percent is good while 70percent is very good.

Objective 1 Table 3: Local government administrative autonomy and the administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria

S/ N	QUESTIONS	Σ fx	X	Decisio n
1	State government bureaucratic structures like the State Universal Basic Education Board contribute to stifling the autonomy of Ihiala local government council.	1244	3.6	Agreed
2	Lack of administrative autonomy for local council authorities impacts negatively on their ability to recruit qualified teachers to deliver effective primary education to the local populace.	1310	3.8	Agreed
3	The state government has better capacity to oversee the activities of the local government, hence, the need for the state government to keep a close eye on the local council authorities in their domain.	984	2.8	Disagree d
4	There is a significant positive relationship between lack of local government administrative autonomy and effective	1345	3.9	Agreed

administration of primary education in Ihiala local government area of Anambra State.

- | | | | | |
|---|---|------|-----|--------|
| 5 | The local government administrative bureaucracy extending to the state capital in Awka through its supervising Ministry of Local Government is a waste of public funds. | 1153 | 3.4 | Agreed |
|---|---|------|-----|--------|

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 indicates the various statements generated in relation to the first research question, which sought to ascertain the effect of local government administrative autonomy on the administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria. Five tentative statements were put forward to elicit responses from the respondents. Four of the statements were accepted, while one was rejected. The respondents in the first statement accepted the notion that state government bureaucratic structures like the State Universal Basic Education Board contribute to stifling the autonomy of Ihiala local government council.

In the second statement, they also accepted the idea that lack of administrative autonomy for local council authorities' impacts negatively on their ability to recruit qualified teachers to deliver effective primary education to the local populace. The respondents, who are residents and stakeholders in the local government,

Objective 2, Table 4: The relationship between local government political autonomy and the provision of health centers in Ihiala local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria

S/N	QUESTIONS	Σ fx	X	Decision
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rejected the idea in the third statement that the state government has better capacity to oversee the activities of the local government, hence, the need for the state government to keep a close eye on the local council authorities in their domain. The last two statements which were accepted stated that there is a significant positive relationship between lack of local government administrative autonomy and effective administration of primary education in Ihiala local government area of Anambra State; and that the local government administrative bureaucracy extending to the state capital in Awka through its supervising Ministry of Local Government is a waste of public funds. The implication of the responses of the respondents to the issues raised with respect to the first research question is that lack of administrative autonomy for the local government affect the effective administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria.

6	Elected local council executives are better positioned and suited to provide the people with primary health centers and other healthcare needs of the people at the grassroots level.	1422	4.2	Agreed
7	The conduct of local government elections by state governments does not allow for effective political participation of the people at the grassroots level.	1341	3.9	Agreed
8	Appointment of sole administrators for local council authorities impacts negatively on their level of performance and accountability to the people.	1279	3.7	Agreed
9	Local council authorities functioning through caretaker chairmen saves the state government the financial burden of conducting frequent local government elections.	899	2.6	Disagreed
10	Credible elections at the local level will help to improve the level of responsiveness and service delivery of the local council executives and legislative members to their local	1311	3.8	Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

In table 4, the focus is on analysing the responses of the respondents to the issues relating to the second research question, which was to ascertain the nature of relationship between local government political autonomy and the provision of health centers in Ihiala local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria. Again, all but one of the five statements put forward was accepted. In the first statement, the respondents aligned with the view that elected local council executives are better positioned and suited to provide the people with primary health

centers and other healthcare needs of the people at the grassroots level. They also agree to the second statement that the conduct of local government elections by state governments does not allow for effective political participation of the people at the grassroots level.

Responding in favour of a democratic local governance framework, the respondents accepted the view in the eighth statement that the appointment of sole administrators for local council authorities impacts negatively on their level of performance and accountability to the people. They also rejected the idea in the ninth

statement that local council authorities functioning through caretaker chairmen saves the state government the financial burden of conducting frequent local government elections. In the final analysis, the position of the respondents with respect to the tenth question which states that credible elections at the local level will help to improve the level of responsiveness and service delivery of the local council executives and legislative members to their local constituencies was accepted. The implication of the responses of the respondents to the second research question which deals on the relationship between local government political autonomy and the provision of health centers in Ihiala local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria is that political autonomy for local council authorities is significant to enhance the provision of health

centers and other essential social services at the rural, local and grassroots levels.

Test of Hypotheses

Data used for the test were obtained from the responses of respondents to various questions in the questionnaire item that relate to the various hypotheses. The hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Simple Regression Models. A 0.05 level of significance was adopted for the study.

Hypothesis One

H₀: Local government administrative autonomy has no significant effect on administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria.

H₁: Local government administrative autonomy has a significant effect on administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.520 ^a	.270	.073	.38057

a. Predictors: (Constant), LG Administrative Autonomy
The table shows the model summary for hypothesis one which states that local government administrative autonomy has no significant effect on administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria. From the summary, the regression coefficient (R) which shows that local government administrative autonomy has a

significant effect on administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria and the R-Square (R²) which shows the percentage change in the dependent variable caused by changes in the independent variable, it is seen that a positive relationship exists between the variables (R = .520).

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	.215	1	.215	1.482	.029 ^b
Residual	.579	4	.145		
Total	.794	5			

a. Dependent Variable: Primary Education

b. Predictors: (Constant), LG Administrative Autonomy

The ANOVA output for test of hypothesis one which states that local government administrative autonomy has no significant effect on administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria. With significance level of 5% (0.05), and comparing it with the probability value (p-value) as represented by sig in the table, the null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternate hypothesis and it is, therefore, stated that local government administrative autonomy will have significant effect on administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria.

Implication

The implication of the finding from the test of the first hypothesis is that as long as state government agencies like the Local Government Service Commission and the Ministry of Local Government continue to tale guide the

Correlations

	L.G. Political Autonomy	Health Centres
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administration of local council authorities, Ihiala local government, like its counterparts in Anambra state, will continue to struggle in its mandate to provide quality primary education to the people in the locality. The meddlesome administrative apparatus of the state government does not allow for uniqueness and peculiarity in addressing the specific needs of the people of Ihiala local government in terms of the administration of primary education.

Hypothesis Two

H₀: There is no significant relationship between local government political autonomy and provision of health centers in Ihiala local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between local government political autonomy and provision of health centers in Ihiala local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

L.G. Political Autonomy	Pearson Correlation	1	.550
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.034
	N	343	343
Health Centres	Pearson Correlation	.550	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.034	
	N	343	343

The result of the correlation coefficient for hypothesis two indicates that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient is 0.550 showing that local government political autonomy has a strong correlation with provision of health centers if implemented at Ihiala local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

Decision Rule: From the computation above, the probability value at 0.034 is less than 0.05 significant level. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis which states there is a significant relationship between local government political autonomy and provision of health centers in Ihiala local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

Implication

The implication of the finding from the test of the second hypothesis is obvious. The inability of the people at the local councils to freely and independently choose their political leaders has telling implication on the administration of the local government. The current situation where the state government continues to handpick local government chairpersons and their councilors

implies that true representation is yet to be entrenched at the local government level. The implication is that important services like healthcare delivery continue to suffer from stagnation, inefficiency and ineffectiveness.

Discussion of Findings

This study was carried out to determine the effect of local government autonomy on rural development in Ihiala Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria. Guided by two research questions and hypotheses, results from the test of hypothesis one led us to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that local government administrative autonomy has a significant effect on administration of primary education in Ihiala local government council of Anambra state, Nigeria. The implication of this finding to the study is that administrative autonomy for local council authorities will help them to better articulate their local needs especially in the area of administering primary education. The finding agrees with the finding of Okirika and Sokoh, (2023) on local government autonomy and the challenges of rural development in Delta south senatorial district of Delta state, Nigeria. The

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study found that there is significant relationship between local government autonomy and rural development. Also, in the study by Anayochukwu, Ani, and Nsah, (2022) on local government autonomy and governance: a case study in Nigeria, it was discovered that state interference in local affairs contributes to a lack of local government autonomy and governance in Nigeria.

Hypothesis two addresses issues relating to the relationship between local government political autonomy and provision of health centers in Ihiala local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria. The test of the second hypothesis led us to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis which states there is a significant relationship between local government political autonomy and provision of health centers in Ihiala local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

Conclusion

Our journey in this study has been on local government autonomy and rural development in Ihiala Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria, guided by two research questions and hypotheses. Going by the findings from this study, it is obvious that local government

3. heir states.

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Ezinwa Precious Onyekwere and Chinyeaka J. Igbokwe-Ibeto

autonomy in its true sense is crucial to the survival and thriving of the local government as a third-tier level of government. However, the inability of the local government to fully control and utilise its available human and material resources as a result of structural imbalances in the system of intergovernmental relationship between local government and other levels of government has remained the bane of the local government system in Nigeria. To this end, this study recommends the following:

1. Local council authorities should be allowed greater flexibility to recruit and manage their personnel in line with their peculiar needs, challenges and resources.
2. Conduct of local government elections should be handled by the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) as have been proposed in the ongoing constitutional amendment by the National Assembly of Nigeria. This is against the current practice of State Independent Electoral Commissions (SIECs) conducting Local Government elections. This will help to reduce the strangulating influence of state governors on who becomes what, when and how in the local governance structure within t

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